

SIMCor

In-Silico testing and validation of Cardiovascular IMplantable devices

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Executive summary

The present document is meant to illustrate the SIMCor *communication and dissemination* (C&D) strategy, along with the relevant activities carried out in the first three months of project implementation. After a brief introduction of *WP2 – Engagement, communication, dissemination and exploitation*, its objectives, task structure and deliverables, the second chapter describes the C&D strategy plan in detail, including connection with exploitation activities. The strategy is articulated into a diversified range of activities, including web communication, dissemination events, publications, multimedia, as well as a range of engagement, feedback gathering, collaboration and cross-dissemination initiatives with relevant stakeholders within consortium partners' contact networks, including institutions, associations, foundations, regulatory bodies and standards committees, as well as other in-silico trial and eHealth research projects. To do so, the consortium will leverage a wide range of communication channels, including project website and social media, events and journals, as well as the support of consortium partners and other partner projects channels. The third chapter will present the activities carried out in M1-M3, including preparation of project branding (i.e., logo, icons, infographics, presentation templates, banners for acknowledgment of funding), communication materials (i.e., a model presentation for external communication), setup of website and social media channels, mapping of consortium channels and stakeholder networks, together with main action items for M6 and beyond.

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Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
C&D	Communication and dissemination
CHA	Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin
BIO	Biotronik SE & Co. KG
ECRIN-ERIC	European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network
EU	European Union
FP6	Sixth framework programme
FP7	Seventh framework programme
GA	Grant Agreement
GSP	Good simulation practices
H2020	Horizon 2020
ICT	Information and communication technologies
IF	Impact Factor
IHS	Institut für Höhere Studien – Institute for Advanced Studies
IIB	Institut für ImplantatTechnologie und Biomaterialien e.V.
IST	In-silico trial
ISW	In Silico World
ISW_CoP	In Silico World Community of Practice
LYN	Lynkeus
M	Month
OA	Open access
PAPS	Pulmonary artery pressure sensors
PC	Project Coordinator
PHI	Philips Electronics Netherlands B.V.
SOP	Standard operating procedure
TUE	Eindhoven University of Technology
TUG	Graz University of Technology
UCL	University College of London
UTBV	Universitatea Transilvania Din Braşov
VPH/VPHi	Virtual Physiological Human Institute for Integrative Biomedical Research VZW
Y	Year
WG	Working group
WP	Work package

Introduction

The integration of in-silico testing solutions into the medical device development, verification, validation and approval workflow represents the fundamental goal of SIMCor. This goal cannot be achieved without a deep connection, engagement and community building activity within the relevant communities of interest at research, clinical and industry level. This not only concerns raising awareness on the developed methodologies and resources, but mostly entails increasing trust on the reliability of in-silico testing solutions for achieving a robust validation, leading to safer and more effective medical devices, at enhanced time- and cost-effectiveness.

As published in the *Virtual Physiological Human* (VPH) Institute original STEP roadmap: *“The success of the emerging VPH will be highly dependent upon the information provided to the potential user community. (...) The existence of some coordinating body will ensure that resource providers can find an easy way of ensuring that the user base becomes aware of their materials at an early stage, assisting rapid uptake.”*¹

This effort cannot be disjointed with an early and continuous liaison with and feedback from regulatory authorities, that have to oversee and approve methodologies, standards and guidelines, to serve as a common standard basis for the whole medical device community.

These concepts represent the basis for the formulation of the SIMCor C&D strategy plan, which has been structured in strict synergy with the project implementation phases, conceiving most appropriate measures according to expected results and relevant dissemination, feedback gathering, exploitation and IPR management needs. The strategy integrates diverse activities, including web-based communication, research and business events, ground-level and specialised publications, specific initiatives for the liaison with regulatory authorities and standard committees in the field, as well as a series of cross-fertilisation activities directed towards relevant research initiatives, patient associations, foundations, including a collaboration with the other research initiatives of the SC1-DTH-06-2020 H2020 Topic Call and other *in-silico trial* (IST) projects through the *In Silico World* (ISW) community, and additional higher-level exchanges with other health ICT projects within the H2020-SC1-DTH-2018-2020 Call.

To carry out such a strategy, the consortium will rely on a series of project-specific communication channels and tools, as well as leverage channels and contact networks pertaining to its consortium partners in their different areas of expertise, maintaining a close cooperation among all members throughout the whole project.

¹ Seeding the EuroPhysiome: A Roadmap to the Virtual Physiological Human (2007), p. 82. Available at https://www.vph-institute.org/upload/step-vph-roadmap-printed-3_5192459539f3c.pdf

WP2 - Engagement, communication, dissemination and exploitation

Key aim and objectives

The aim of WP2, as illustrated in the Grant Agreement *Document of Work* (DoW), is to engage with the variety of project-related stakeholders (i.e., *IT researchers and developers, device manufacturers, regulatory authorities, physicians and clinical researchers*) and largely disseminate the rationale, objectives and solutions deployed within SIMCor among them, laying the basis for the subsequent exploitation of project results, as well as its broader communication to the wider public, including *patients and their associations, mass media and citizens at large*.

Particularly, WP2 will pursue some specific objectives:

1. **Communicate project rationale, mission, overall methodology and outcomes** to the different stakeholders and the wider public.
2. **Engage with representatives of project groups of interest** for communication, dissemination, involvement and feedback gathering throughout the project implementation.
3. **Disseminate project research outcomes to the relevant communities of interest** in the clinical and ICT domains, leveraging on the huge outreach potential of the VPH and LYN.
4. **Analyse the exploitation potential for the implemented tools**, in terms of both individual exploitation routes and joint initiatives, design and put in place appropriate exploitation strategies.
5. **Coordinate the IPR management of SIMCor results**, including Open Access of research data and results, and future integration into the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

Tasks and deliverables

The WP will be led by *Lynkeus* (LYN, P2 of SIMCor), that will carry out most of tasks and deliverables, but leveraging contribution from the whole consortium in terms of stakeholder engagement and dissemination of results within their networks. The *Virtual Physiological Human Institute* (VPH, P12 of SIMCor) will be leader of *T2.3 - Liaison with regulatory authorities*, as a prerequisite for receiving feedback and approval on standards, guidelines and *standard operating procedures* (SOPs) developed in the context of *WP4 - Definition of standard operating procedures*.

Tasks	Deliverables
T2.1: Communication and dissemination strategy, branding and tools (LYN/ALL, M1-M36)	D2.1: Project presentation (LYN, M1) D2.2: Communication and dissemination strategy plan (LYN, M3) D2.3: Communication channels and materials (LYN, M36)
T2.2: Dissemination events (LYN/ALL, M1-M36)	D2.4: Dissemination events (LYN, M36)
T2.3: Liaison with regulatory authorities (VPH/ALL, M1-M36)	D2.5: Regulatory feedback report (1) (VPH, M19) D2.6: Regulatory feedback report (2) (VPH, M31)
T2.4: Exploitation planning (LYN/ALL, M19-M36)	D2.7: IPR and exploitation plan (LYN, M36)
T2.5: IPR management, open research and sustainability (LYN/ALL, M19-M36)	

Table 1: WP2 - Engagement, communication, dissemination and exploitation tasks and deliverables, including C&D tasks (light blue), liaison with regulatory authorities (green) and exploitation activities (grey).

Figure 1: WP2 - Engagement, communication, dissemination and exploitation Gantt chart.

WP dependencies

WP2 activity will be closely linked to the other WPs, on various levels. WP3-9 will provide scientific results and resources to be disseminated throughout project implementation, including the platform itself (WP3), SOPs (WP4), data (WP5-6), virtual cohorts (WP7), models for virtual device implantation and effect simulation (WP8-9). On the other hand, WP10 will produce the evaluation of project results impact on healthcare, medical device industry and market and the society as a whole, that will constitute the basis for increasing trust of future platform users, as well as support the broader communication on the project impact to patient associations, mass media and citizens. Lastly, WP2 will work in connection with WP1, that will give indications on the evolution of project activities to plan C&D activities in coordination with major project achievements and milestones.

Figure 2: Interactions of WP2 - Engagement, communication, dissemination and exploitation with other WPs.

Communication and dissemination strategy plan

Project stakeholder groups and target audiences

Due to its ambitious goal, SIMCor will target a wide series of stakeholder groups of interest at academic, industrial, clinical and societal level, including: (1) *the healthcare ICT and economics research community*; (2) *the medical device industry*; (3) *regulatory authorities and standards committees*, (4) *the clinical cardiology community*; (5) *patients and their associations*, (6) *mass media, policy makers and society at large*. These target communities have been categorised into *a) primary audiences*, to be engaged for dissemination and exploitation of results, communication and feedback gathering on project solutions throughout project implementation; *b) secondary audiences*, to be involved for public discussion, citizen science approaches and general communication.

N	Stakeholder group	Individuals	Goals
<i>a) Primary audiences (dissemination, exploitation, feedback gathering and communication)</i>			
1	Health ICT and economics research community	biomedical engineers biophysicists IT specialists entrepreneurs	1) boost research on computer simulations by making available data, knowledge and standards 2) promote investments on in-silico technologies 3) accelerate translation into the market
2	Medical device industry	economists social scientists	
3	Regulatory authorities	medical device control standards committees data infrastructure networks	Setting standards for computer modelling solutions in collaboration with regulators
4	Clinical cardiology community	cardiologists cardiac surgeons caregivers hospital directors medical associations clinical data analysts	1) foster awareness and promote adoption of in-silico clinical trial technology 2) accelerate translation of in-silico tested medical devices into the clinics 3) increasing trust on reliability, efficacy, safety and cost-effectiveness of computer based simulations
<i>b) Secondary audiences (citizen science and general communication)</i>			
5	Patient community	cardiologic patients patients' families patient associations	1) increase patients' trust in the use of in-silico-tested medical devices in clinical practice 2) build understanding of the benefits in terms of enhanced patient safety, reduction of animal testing and economic value creation
6	Mass media, policy makers and society at large	journalists healthcare authorities citizens	

Table 2: Project stakeholder groups, corresponding target audiences and relevant C&D goals.

Partners roles and reference communities

The coordination of the whole C&D activity will be on LYN, that as a research strategy consultancy specialised in digital health innovation can boast a consolidated experience in exploitation, C&D of major ICT for health-related FP6, FP7² and H2020³ research and innovation programs, and a thick network of businesses, research and healthcare institutions including *Big Data Value Association (BDVA)*, *Healthcare Information and Management Systems Society (HIMSS)*, *Research Data Alliance*

² FP6-7: Health-e-Child, Sim-e-Child, MD-Paedigree, Cardioproof, Avicenna

³ H2020: MyHealthMyData, euCanSHare, KRAKEN, euCanImage

(RDA). Another major contribution will be provided by VPH, leading the liaison with regulatory authorities and contributing to engagement and dissemination within its open community of scientists, clinicians and healthcare organisations, as well as leveraging its collaboration with industry leaders in the field of in-silico medicine in the Avicenna Alliance. Academic IT partners (IIB, TUE, TUG, UTBV) will contribute to C&D within the ICT for health community, IHS in the healthcare economics and social science area, industry leaders (BIO, PHI) will contribute on the business side, while clinical research partners (CHA, UCL, ECRIN) will be active within the clinical community. A more comprehensive illustration of partners' roles and relevant affiliated communities is provided below, followed by a list of relevant stakeholder communities with affiliated societies and associations.

Figure 3: Partners' C&D roles and reference communities.

Consortium partners' stakeholder networks: affiliated societies and associations

Community	Network: affiliated academic institutions, industries, societies, associations
Healthcare ICT and in-silico medicine	Avicenna Alliance, Big Data Value Association (BDVA), Healthcare Information and Management Systems Society (HIMSS), Research Data Alliance (RDA), European Community on Computational Methods in Applied Sciences (ECCMAS), Eindhoven MedTech Innovation Center (e/MTIC)
Medical device industry	Jotec GmbH, Medtronic, German Medical Technology Association (BVMed), Striker, Boston Scientific, Johnson & Johnson, Novartis, Zimmer, MedTechEurope, Cardiomed SRL, Siemens SRL
Biophysics and bioengineering	IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology (EMB), European Society of Biomechanics (ESB), Engineering Mechanics Graduate School, German Academy of Engineering (ACATECH), University Politehnica Bucharest
Health economics and public health	European Health Economics Association (EuHEA), European Health Policy Group (EHPG), European Public Health Association (EUPHA)
Cardiology and clinical research	European Society of Cardiology (ESC), Association for European Paediatric and Congenital Cardiology (AEPC), Heart Failure Society of America (HFSA), Heart Rhythm Society (HRS), European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI), Medical Infrastructure Users Forum (MIUF), Drug Information Association (DIA), Society for Clinical Trials (SCT), School for Cardiovascular diseases of Maastricht University (CARIM), University of Medicine and Pharmacy Carol Davila

Table 3: Communities of reference of consortium partners and relevant networks of academic institutions, industries, societies and associations.

Regulatory bodies and standards committees

Domain	Regulatory bodies, standard committees
Medical device control	The European Association for Medical Devices of Notified Bodies (TEAM NB), Clinical Decision Support Consortium (CDS Consortium), Food and Drug Administration (FDA) - Office of Science and Engineering Laboratories (OSEL), National Institute for Health Research (NIHR), Office of the National Coordinator for Health Information Technology (ONC), Online Analytical Processing (OLAP), TUV SUD, British Standards Institution (BSI)
Pharmaceutical control	European Medicines Agency (EMA), European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations (EFPIA), Association of the British Pharmaceutical Industry (ABPI), National Institute for Health Research (NIHR), National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE), UK Medicines & Healthcare products Regulatory Agency
Standardisation	International Organization for Standardization (ISO), exp. ISO/TC 150 - Implants for surgery, ASTM INTERNATIONAL - Subcommittee F04.30 Cardiovascular Standards, DIN NA 027-05-06 AA Heart and Vascular Implants, European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI), American National Standards Institute (ANSI), European Committee for Standardization (CEN)
Open science infrastructures	European Open Science Cloud Initiative (EOSC), European Open Science Infrastructure (OpenAIRE), open Electronic Health Records (openEHR), Virtual Manuscript Room (VMR), Open Grid, Open Cloud, Distributed Management Task Force (DMTF), Cloud Security Alliance (CSA), Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM), National Electrical Manufacturers Association (NEMA), Health Level 7 (HL7), Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR)

Table 4: Regulatory bodies, standard committees and open science infrastructures to be engaged for dissemination and availability of results, feedback and approval of SOPs and methodologies.

Patient associations

Patient association	Description
European Patients Forum (EPF)	Umbrella organisation that works with patients' groups in public health and health advocacy across Europe. EPF members represent specific chronic disease groups at EU level or are national coalitions of patients (Belgium)
Healthwatch	Statutory body whose purpose is to understand the needs, experiences and concerns of people who use health and social care services and to speak out on their behalf and share information to improve health and social care services (United Kingdom).
Nakos	National coordinator of patient groups based in Berlin, also represented in the G-BA Federal Joint Commission (Germany).
Health First Europe	A non-profit, non-commercial alliance of patients, healthcare workers, academics and healthcare experts as well as the medical technology industry (Belgium)
International Alliance of Patient Organisations (IAPO)	Global alliance committed to improving the lives of patients from all around the world (Global).
Kardionetzwerk	The cardio network is a German non-profit association, based in Berlin, that is committed to better care and comprehensive education for patients with heart disease. Its internet platform offers all important information about diagnosis, treatment and therapy of cardiovascular diseases, while direct contact with patients is sought through information events in which specialists give lectures and discussion groups. The cardio network also uses political groundwork to ensure that all patients can benefit from innovative care offers (Germany).

Table 5: Patient associations at national, EU and global level to be engaged for project C&D.

Relevant research initiatives

SC1-DTH-06-2020 Topic Call projects

Project	Coordinator	Mission
SimInSitu (In-silico Development- and Clinical-Trial-Platform for Testing in-situ Tissue Engineered Heart Valves)	4RealSim Services BV	Development of a sophisticated in-silico method to predict the short- and long-term behaviour of in-situ tissue engineered heart valves by combining advanced tissue remodelling algorithms with a personalized virtual heart modelling approach.
ISW (In Silico World: Lowering barriers to ubiquitous adoption of In Silico Trials)	Alma Mater Studiorum - Universita Di Bologna	Accelerate the uptake of modelling and simulation technologies for the development and regulatory assessment of all kinds of medical products.
SimCardioTest (Simulation of Cardiac Devices & Drugs for in-silico Testing and Certification)	Institut National De Recherche En Informatique Et Automatique	Creation of an integrated and secure platform standardising & bridging model simulations, in-silico trials, and certification support.

Table 6: SC1-DTH-06-2020 Topic Call projects with ongoing collaboration on development of standards and guidelines, engagement of regulatory authorities and standards committees, research methodology and C&D.

IST research projects (part of the ISW community)

Project	Mission
Disc4all	Training network to advance integrated computational simulations in translational medicine, applied to intervertebral disc degeneration.
INSILC	INSILC is developing a platform for the design of drug-eluting <i>bioresorbable vascular scaffolds</i> (BVS) and a pre-operative planning tool.
INSIST	INSIST is developing a simulator for thrombectomy, expected to be used for the CE marking of new medical devices for such operation.
PIC - Personalised In-Silico Cardiology	Personalised In Silico Cardiology (PIC) is the Marie Curie Training Network ITN that is training a cohort of 15 future innovation leaders able to articulate and materialise the vision of Personalised In-silico Cardiology where healthcare is guided by in-silico models.
SILICOFCM	SILICOFCM is developing a platform for the development and simulation of patient-specific models of the heart, to be used to evaluate the safety and efficacy of new interventions.
STRITUVAD	Pursuing qualification with EMA of a simulator of pulmonary TB infection.
REPOTRIAL	REPOTRIAL is about in-silico repurposing of two drugs and validation with animal models.
CompBioMed	CompBioMed is one of the Council of Europe in high performance computing funded by the e-infrastructures unit. It is entirely dedicated to the development and scalability support of computational medicine solutions, some of which are IST solutions.

Table 7: Other IST projects involved in the ISW Community of Practice, to engage for feedback and collaboration.

Other relevant EU-funded initiatives

Project	Mission
euCanShare (2018-2022)	A joint EU-Canada project to establish a cross-border data sharing and multi-cohort cardiovascular research platform. The project will integrate data infrastructures, IT solutions and data sources from EU, Canada and other countries into a web-based data access system with functionalities for increased efficiency in cardiovascular data-driven research.
BigData@Heart (2017-2022)	With the ultimate aim to improve patient outcomes and reduce the societal burden of atrial fibrillation, acute coronary syndrome and heart failure (HF) in Europe and globally, BigData@Heart will develop a data-driven translational research platform of unparalleled scale and phenotypic resolution.
EUPATI (2018-2020)	A pan-European public-private partnership across the pharmaceutical industry, academia, not-for-profit and patient organisations, focusing on education and training about the process of medicines development, to increase the capacity and capability of patients to be valuable contributors to medicines research and also improve the availability of objective, reliable, independent, patient-friendly information for the public.

Table 8: Other relevant EU-funded projects and other public initiatives relevant for C&D and cross-fertilisation.

C&D strategy: phases of implementation

As previously mentioned, the structure of the C&D phases will be articulated in coordination with the general project implementation structure, illustrated below together with its milestones. Phase 1 (M1-M6) is dedicated to gathering requirements for the platform and the other virtual data generation and modelling activities, as well as to obtaining ethical clearance on project research activities. Phase 2 (M7-M18) is dedicated to the development of in-silico modelling resources, including the platform itself, virtual cohorts, anatomical and functional models for device implantation and effect simulation, SOPs. Phase 3 (M19-M30) is devoted to proof-of concept validation, refinement and finalisation of in-silico resources and impact assessment.

Figure 4: Project implementation phases with relevant objectives and milestones.

Consistently, Phase I (M1-M12) of C&D will be a preparatory phase, dedicated to laying the bases of the actual activity by the formulation of the overall C&D strategy, the analysis of project stakeholders and relevant audiences as well as consortium stakeholder networks, the creation of project branding, communication channels and tools, and an initial community building and general communication. With the achievements of first project results (M12), Phase II (M13-M30) will be devoted to the actual dissemination of results through publications and events, impact assessment-based communication, together with stakeholder engagement, audience enlargement and consolidation and, after M18, to feedback gathering on developed solutions, analysis of exploitation opportunities and formulation of relevant strategies.

Phase III (M31-M36), in the last six months of the project, will entail the gathering of final strategic feedback from stakeholders on in-silico solutions, finalisation and put in place of exploitation and IPR management strategies and the platform sustainability plan.

Figure 5: Project C&D strategy plan, including relevant phases, objectives and activities.

Communication channels and tools

The consortium will leverage a wide range of C&D channels and tools, pertaining to all kinds of audiences (e.g., website, social media) or specialised audiences (e.g., peer-review publications, dissemination events). These, illustrated in the table below, summarily include:

- **Web channels:** *project website and social network accounts (Twitter, YouTube) and a publication repository (Zenodo)*, to be populated on a regular basis with project news, publications and achievements, further contributing to the growth of dedicated communities of stakeholders;
- **Print-based materials:** *brochures, posters*, at project inception, for general communication purposes, and in correspondence with specific events (e.g., conference posters on research results);
- **Multimedia:** *photos* (e.g., at dissemination events, project meetings), *videos* (e.g., interviews, teaser clips, demos of the platform and tools) to be spread through website and social media;
- **Dissemination events:** *medical, academic and business conferences*, to be attended by consortium partners' representatives in the relevant fields; *project-organised workshops* within healthcare ICT events, for demoing in-silico solutions, *industrial workshops* at industrial partners' premises, webinars directed to researchers and medical device manufacturers and *clinical focus groups* at clinical partners' centres;
- **Publications:** *peer-review publications* (e.g., journal or conference proceedings articles), *generalists publications* (e.g., newspaper or magazine articles, press releases, annual project e-newsletter).

Besides these, the consortium will also leverage **consortium partners' institutional communication channels and tools**, illustrated in a few pages, including *websites, social media, press releases, mailing lists* and much more. To do so, the consortium will establish a *C&D working group* (C&D-WG) that will entail representatives of all partners, particularly Communications Officers and Press Office reference professionals, to jointly plan and put in place some agreed C&D initiatives.

Besides, the consortium will also count on the support of **C&D channels pertaining to the other projects of the SC1-DTH-06-2020 Call Topic (*Accelerating the uptake of computer simulations for testing medicines and medical devices*)**, the representatives of which have gathered in a first telco on 25/02/2021 for mutual introduction and planning of collaboration initiatives on C&D, regulatory authorities' engagement and other topics of common interest (e.g., SOPs development).

Ultimately, the consortium will utilise, where appropriate, **communication tools made available by the European Commission**, such as publications (e.g., Horizon Magazine, Project stories, research*eu results magazine, research*eu focus), online news (e.g., headlines, CORDIS Wire), audiovisual (e.g., Futuris Magazine), events and conferences, following communication guidelines for Horizon 2020 project participants⁴.

⁴ Communicating EU research and innovation guidance for project participants. Version 1.0 - 25 September 2014. Available at https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/gm/h2020-guide-comm_en.pdf.

Web channels

Project website

The project website (URL www.simcor-h2020.eu), currently being finalised and to be released at the beginning of M4, is structured in the following sections, described below.

- **Home:** overview of project mission and objectives, news, acknowledgments of EU funding and contacts.

Figure 6: Preview of the project website home page.

- **About:** more in-depth description of project rationale, mission and strategic objectives, clinical focus, implementation phases.

Figure 7: Preview of the project website "About" section.

- **Consortium:** geographical localisation and description of project partners and their role in the project.

Figure 8: Preview of the project website "Consortium" section.

- **Publications & materials:** title, info and open access link (publisher’s website for open access publications, or Zenodo) of peer-review publications, public deliverables and press releases, as well as others to be possibly added later on (e.g., posters, presentations, educational publications, etc.).

Figure 9: Preview of the project website “Publications & materials” section.

- **News:** short posts on project news, achievements, project meetings and public events, publications.

Figure 10: Preview of the project website “News” section.

- **Contact:** contact form for request for information or other inquiries.

Figure 11: Preview of the project website “Contact” section.

Social media

Twitter was activated in M1 and is currently making connections with relevant organisations to create its followers audience. For the moment, we have suspended the creation of a project page on ResearchGate (which had been foreseen in the Grant Agreement), as no-one in the consortium is a ResearchGate user, and we believe the outreach would be limited. However, we will activate a YouTube account and channel in concomitance with the production of the first multimedia (i.e., teaser video and interviews), and the creation of other accounts (e.g., LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram) will also be considered.

Twitter

Figure 12: Preview of the project Twitter account page.

Dissemination events

The consortium will leverage a wide range of dissemination events. These entails **research, business and medical conferences** organised in the context of relevant fields, that consortium partners' representatives will attend as simple auditors or speakers, for networking and results dissemination, as well as a series of **project-organised events**, including:

- **Workshops** to be held in the context of **healthcare ICT events**, at the presence of the relevant academic and industrial communities, for platform and in-silico solutions demo and feedback gathering;
- **Industrial workshops** to be held at industrial partners' premises, with special regards to engagement and feedback from the medical device manufacturers community;
- **Webinars**, directed to academic and industrial audiences, for platform demo and discussion in small groups of interest;
- **Clinical focus groups** with cardiologists and other clinicians, to be held at clinical partners' premises.

Type	Scope	Audience	Timeframe	Partners
Medical, academic and business conferences <i>Biomedical engineering, in-silico medicine, ICT for health, cardiology, health economics, social sciences</i>	Dissemination of results & networking	Academic, industrial, clinical	M1 – M36	ALL
Workshops within healthcare ICT events	Demo & feedback gathering	academic, industrial	M18, M36	ALL
Industrial workshops			M19-M36	BIO, PHI
Webinars				ALL
Clinical focus groups	Increasing the trust of the medical community	clinical		CHA, UCL

Table 9: Overview of dissemination event to be attended (light blue) or organised (turquoise) by consortium partners or the whole consortium in the course of the project.

A list of candidate annual conferences in the relevant research, business and clinical fields, to be considered for results dissemination, is reported below.

Field	Conferences, workshops, scientific sessions
Biomedical engineering	Congress of the European Society of Biomechanics (ESB), European Medical and Biomedical Engineering Congress (EMBEC), Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention (MICCAI). <i>Others:</i> Annual Conference of the German Society for Biomedical Engineering (BMT), Biomedical Engineering Society (BMES) Annual Meeting, Computing in Cardiology (CinC) Conference, Conference of the German Association for Laser Anemometry (GALA), Conference of the German Society for Biomedical Engineering (BMT), Conference on functional imaging and modelling of the heart (FIMH), European Society of Biomechanics Congress (ESB), Fluids Engineering Division Summer Meeting (FEDSM), IEEE Bioinformatics and Bioengineering Conference (BIBE), IEEE Conference on Bioinformatics and Biomedicine (BIBM), IEEE Conference on Information Technology and Applications in Biomedicine (ITAB), IEEE International Symposium on Biomedical Imaging (ISBI), Information Processing in Medical Imaging Conference (IPMI), International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC), International Conference on Biomedical Engineering (ICBME), International Conference on Computational Bioengineering (ICCB), International Conference on Computational Science (ICCS), International Conference on Modelling and Simulation (IASTED), International Joint Conference on Biomedical Engineering Systems and Technologies (BIOSTEC), International Society of Biomechanics (ISB) Congress, International Symposium on Biomechanics in Vascular Biology and Cardiovascular Disease, Symposium of the American Medical Informatics Association (AMIA), World Congress of Biomechanics (WCB), World Congress on Computational Mechanics (WCCM), World Congress on Medical Physics and Biomedical Engineering (IUPESM)

Cardiology	European Society of Cardiology (ESC), Transcatheter Cardiovascular Therapeutics Conference (TCT), European Association for Cardio-Thoracic Surgeons Annual Meeting (EACTS), Virtual Physiological Human (VPH) conference, Computer Assisted Radiology and Surgery Congress (CARS). <i>Others:</i> European Society of Radiology (ESR), American Heart Association (AHA) Scientific Sessions, American Society for Artificial Internal Organs Conference (ASAIO), Annual Meeting of the European Association of Cardiovascular Imaging (EACVI), Conference on Functional Image and Modelling of the Heart (FIMH), European Community on Computational Methods in Applied Sciences Congress (ECCOMAS), European Society for Artificial Organs Congress (ESAO), Congress, Heart Failure Association (HFA) of the ESC Annual Meeting, Heart Failure Society of America (HFSA) Annual Meeting, International Clinical Trial Day (ICTD), International Society for Magnetic Resonance Annual Meeting (ISMRM), Mathematical Methods in Biomedical Image Analysis, IEEE workshop (MMBIA), Radiological Society of North America Annual Meeting (RSNA), Society for Cardiovascular Magnetic Resonance Annual Scientific Sessions (SCMR), SPIE Medical Imaging Conference, Summer Biomechanics, Bioengineering, and Biotransport Conference (SB3C), Veith Symposium on Vascular and Endovascular Issues, Workshop Bildverarbeitung in der Medizin (BVI), World Congress of Cardiology (WCC)
Economics, social sciences	European Public Health Association (EuPHA) Conference, European Health Economics Association (EUHEA) Conference. <i>Others:</i> European Forum Alpbach, European Health Forum Gastein (EHFG), European Health Management Association (EHMA) Annual Conference, International Health Economics Association (IHEA) World Congress

Table 10: List of candidate research conferences to be attended for dissemination of results in relevant fields.

Publications

Project publications include **peer-review publications** (e.g., journal or conference proceedings articles) and **generalists publications** (newspaper or magazine articles, press releases, annual project e-newsletter).

Peer-review publications

Specialists publications will mostly include **journal or conference proceedings articles** in relevant fields, to be disseminated through website, Twitter and made available in *open access* (OA) through the Zenodo platform. A preliminary selection of candidate publications in each relevant field is reported below, along with OA publication status and *impact factor* (IF).

Field	Journal	OA status ⁵	IF ⁶
Biomedical engineering	International Journal of High Performance Computing Applications	OA	1.060
	IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering	OA	1.418
	Biomechanics and Modeling in Mechanobiology	hybrid	2.829
	Biophysical Journal	hybrid	2.845
	BMC Bioinformatics	hybrid	3.424
	Computational Physics	hybrid	5.768
	Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine	hybrid	1.725
	Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering	hybrid	7.816
	ESAIM: Mathematical Modelling and Numerical Analysis	hybrid	4.491
	IEEE Transactions of Biomedical Engineering	OA	3.950
	IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging	hybrid	2.025
	International Journal for Numerical Methods in Biomedical Engineering	hybrid	2.731
	International Journal of Online and Biomedical Informatics	hybrid	3.093
	International Journal of Technology Assessment in Health Care	OA	4.428
	Journal of Biomechanical Engineering	hybrid	2.829
	Journal of Biomechanics	hybrid	4.821
	Journal of Computational Physics	hybrid	2.845
	Medical & Biological Engineering & Computing	hybrid	4.491
Medical Engineering and Physics	hybrid	7.816	
Open Biomedical Engineering Journal	hybrid	2.576	

⁵ Gold open access options: OA (open access journal, i.e., all articles open access by default, free of charge), hybrid (hybrid journal supporting open access, i.e., open access can be obtained upon payment of a dedicated open access fee).

⁶ Source: <https://mjl.clarivate.com>

Cardiology, clinical research	American Heart Journal	hybrid	4.023
	American Journal of Physiology-Heart and Circulatory Physiology	hybrid	4.048
	Circulation	hybrid	23.054
	Circulation Research	hybrid	15.862
	Clinical Trials	hybrid	2.715
	Controlled Clinical Trials	hybrid	1.000
	European Heart Journal	hybrid	24.889
	Heart	hybrid	5.082
	IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging	hybrid	7.816
	International Journal of Cardiology USFD	hybrid	3.471
	Journal of Cardiovascular Magnetic Resonance	OA	5.070
	Journal of Magnetic Resonance Imaging	hybrid	3.732
	Journal of the American College of Cardiology	hybrid	18.639
	Journal of Thoracic Surgery	OA	5.261
	Lancet	hybrid	59.102
	Magnetic Resonance in Medicine	hybrid	3.858
	Medical Image Analysis	hybrid	8.880
	New England Journal of Medicine	hybrid	70.670
	Simulation in Healthcare	hybrid	2.241
The Internet Journal of Medical Simulation	OA	4.945	
Trials	OA	1.975	
Economics, social sciences	BMC Health Services Research	OA	1.932
	Health Affairs	N/A	5.711
	Journal of Business Research	hybrid	4.028
	Journal of Medical Internet Research	hybrid	4.945
	Social Sciences and Medicine	hybrid	3.087
	Socio-economic Planning Sciences	hybrid	2.196

Table 11: List of candidate research publications where to submit scientific papers for dissemination of project results in relevant fields, including open access policy and impact factor.

Open access policy

Following EC's guidelines for dissemination of project results⁷, all project publications will be made available in OA upon publication or after embargo period, if any, in any case within six months after publication. To do so, the consortium will publish as much as possible on OA journals, or else make the full-text available (as published version, pre-print or accepted manuscript) in the Zenodo project archive, and possibly other sources as well (e.g., institutional archives, others).

Figure 13: Open access modalities to be adopted for project-related publications.

⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/open-access_en.htm

A preview of the project-related Zenodo archive, developed in M1, is reported below.

The screenshot shows the Zenodo website interface. At the top, there is a blue navigation bar with the Zenodo logo, a search bar, and links for 'Upload' and 'Communities'. The user's email address 'annarizzo85@gmail.com' is visible in the top right. Below the navigation bar, the main heading reads 'SIMCor (In-Silico testing and validation of Cardiovascular IMplantable devices)'. Underneath, there is a 'Recent uploads' section with a search bar containing the same project name and a 'More' button. To the right, there is a green 'New upload' button and a 'Community' section. The community section features the SIMCor logo, which consists of a stylized blue and green circuit-like graphic above the text 'SIMCor'. Below the logo, the community title is repeated: 'SIMCor (In-Silico testing and validation of Cardiovascular IMplantable devices)'. A short description follows: 'SIMCor is a 3-year (2021-2023) Research and Innovation Action funded under the topic SC1-DTH-06-2020 (Accelerating the uptake of computer simulations for testing medicines and medical devices) of the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme. The project is developing an open, reusable, cloud-based platform for in-silico development, validation and regulatory approval of cardiovascular implantable devices. The platform'.

Figure 14: Preview of the Zenodo project community.

Consortium institutional channels

Besides official project channels and tools, the project will count on the support of the channels and tools of its consortium institutions, indicated in the table below, that will be used to further share and circulate project-related contents and materials (e.g., re-tweeting posts, sharing videos, circulating press releases). Also, a *C&D working group* (C&D-WG) is being set up, including the project C&D Manager (LYN) and representatives of consortium partners' press offices (CHA, BIO, IHS, PHI, TUE, TUG, UCL) or communications officers (ECRIN, VPH), and will e-meet on a periodic basis to exchange ideas, coordinate and plan joint C&D initiatives together.

Partner	Website	Twitter	Facebook	LinkedIn	Instagram	YouTube	Newsletter	Press releases	Mailing list
CHA	✓	✓	✓		✓			✓	
LYN	✓	✓	✓	✓					
BIO	✓	✓		✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
ECRIN	✓	✓		✓			✓	✓	
IHS	✓	✓		✓			✓	✓	
IIB	✓								
PHI	✓	✓							
TUE	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	
TUG	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
UCL	✓	✓							
UTBV	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓			
VPH	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 12: Overview of consortium institutional channels to be leveraged for project C&D.

The SC1-DTH-06-2020 collaboration

On 25/02/2021, the first telco between SC1-DTH-06-2020 projects representatives took place on initiative of our consortium. After some greetings and introductions, project representatives discussed some possible collaboration pathways, including:

- communication and dissemination (cross-dissemination and connection of channels);
- engagement with regulators and standards committees (FDA, EMA, TeamNB, ISO) with the support of the VPH Institute and the Avicenna Alliance (partner of 3 out of 4 projects);
- formulation of guidelines, *good simulation practices* (GSP) and SOPs;
- exchange and feedback on R&D, verification and validation methodologies.

What emerged in the course of the call is quite fundamental for what concerns future engagement with regulatory authorities and the in-silico medicine community at large. The VPH institute (partner in 3 projects of the call) and Avicenna Alliance have been building for quite some years on an active relation and cooperation with competent authorities, including FDA, EMA, TeamNB and ISO committees. The first tangible results are now coming out, with joint white papers and guidelines for the regulation of in-silico technologies in drugs and devices, and the roll-out of a GSP grass roots initiative. These interactions will ensure the projects in this Topic Call can hit the ground running and will have direct access to relevant interlocutors within the competent authorities.

SIMCor, SimInSitu and SimCardioTest are “vertical” projects, where some ICT applications are being developed on some specific use cases, along with the development of more generalised methods and SOPs. The ISW project, by contrast, represents a “horizontal” project, not aimed to develop a specific technology, but rather to develop synergies with other initiatives working in the in-silico medicine space, in order to help all developers to lower the barriers around the adoption of in-silico medicine. For this reason, ISW is focused on leading a wider collaboration between not only the SC1-DTH-06-2020, but also all projects, representative organisations and other actors under the umbrella of *its In Silico World Community of Practice* (ISW_CoP)⁸, in alignment and with the support and participation of the VPH Institute and the Avicenna Alliance.

The ISW_CoP is an online community, based on Slack and predating the ISW project, where organisations and individuals working on in-silico medicine (currently +350) can participate in collective online discussions. The ISW_CoP Slack channel includes public channels, open to all interested members willing to join, and invitation-only private channels, that can be opened on request. Of note, the ISW_CoP community also includes a private channel (i.e., *IST_Research_Projects*), reserved to the partners of relevant EC-funded research projects (see relevant table in the previous paragraph), as a forum to collaborate and set up joint initiatives.

The ISW PC invited the representatives of other projects to join the community, the membership of which is open and free of charge and participate in the discussions to confront other experts from the in-silico community and get feedback on methodologies and guidelines under development, while VPH will represent the interface with the regulatory authorities and committees on behalf of all projects, and all participants agreed on this approach.

Also, ISW is in the process of developing an Associate Partner role in the project, that will get preferential access to some of the resources under development and be able to contribute to ISW-driven consensus processes our project will drive, and ISW is going to send an invitation to the other SC1-DTH-06-2020 projects in due time.

⁸ <https://insilico.world/community/>

WP2 activity: M1-M6 and beyond

Activity of the first trimester: M1-M3

M1: branding, communication channels setup and project presentation

The first month of the project was dedicated to a series of preparatory activities, including:

- **Elaboration of a series of 3 project logo proposals**, that have been submitted to the consortium, and among which **the final SIMCor logo** was chosen through a web survey (via SurveyMonkey);

Figure 15: Initial series of logo proposals among which the final SIMCor logo was selected through e-survey.

- **Preparation of the ppt presentation template**, based on the chosen logo graphic, that was used for kick-off meeting presentations and, in turn, for the **elaboration of a preliminary model project overview presentation for C&D purposes**;

Figure 16: Presentation template prepared for the kick-off and subsequent meetings, as well as for C&D purposes.

- **Elaboration of the one- and two-row version of the project banner for acknowledgment of funding**, to be used in all project C&D materials;

Figure 17: Two-rows and one-row version of the banner for acknowledgment of EU funding.

- **Drafting of a project-overview high-level description** to be used for project website and other C&D materials (reported in *D2.1 – Project presentation*);
- **Setup of project social media (Twitter) and publication repository (Zenodo)**;
- **Preparation and launch of a first press release announcing project inception**, circulated in concomitance of the kick-off meeting, reported in *D1.2 – Kick-off meeting report (LYN, M2)*.

M2-M3: consortium channels and stakeholders, strategy conception, website implementation

The second and third month of the project have been dedicated to prosecuting preparatory activities, including:

- **Conception, design and implementation of the project website**;
- **Elaboration of project icons and infographics**;
- **Analysis and mapping of consortium partners' communication channels, communication officers and/or press offices professionals and stakeholder networks**, as well as relevant research initiatives, associations and foundations, through an internal consortium survey and web-based research;
- **Elaboration of the present C&D strategy plan**;
- **Setup of the SC1-DTH-06-2020 projects collaboration group**.

Action items for M6 and beyond

By the end of M6, the consortium intends to conclude the **analysis and consolidation of the stakeholder list** and complete the **production of project C&D materials** (e.g., brochure, poster), as illustrated in the scheme below. Based on contacts provided by consortium partners, the WP Leader will also proceed with **the creation of the C&D-WG** with partners' representatives, communication officers and press office professionals and start relevant e-meetings (frequency to be defined).

Figure 18: C&D action items for M1-M6.

After M6 and until M12, the consortium will complete its preparatory phase by **consolidating its stakeholder list and start engaging relevant entities through website and social media, produce some multimedia** (e.g., a teaser video and some interviews to consortium partner's representatives), and prepare **a first project e-newsletter** (in the form of an individual newsletter, or possibly as a SC1-DTH-06-2020 Topic Call project group newsletter), to be released by M12.

Appendix

SIMCor logo proposals

Logo 1 (current official SIMCor logo)

Figure 19: Logo proposal 1, chosen through web survey as the final project logo.

Logo 2 (discarded)

Figure 20: Logo proposal 2, discarded through web survey.

Logo 3 (discarded)

Figure 21: Logo proposal 3, discarded through web survey.